

Naturalista sicil., S. IV, XLVII (1), 2023, pp. 155-157

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8165034>

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BEEPATH: A CITIZEN SCIENCE APPROACH TO THE STUDY
OF THE HONEY BEE HEALTH

*BEEPATH: un approccio di citizen science allo studio
della salute delle api mellifere*

Western honey bees (*Apis mellifera* Linnaeus, 1758) are crucial to global food production (LEONHARDT *et al.*, 2013]. In addition to direct hive products, they provide pollination to wild and cultivated plants, thus contributing to keeping both natural – and agroecosystems healthy. Unfortunately, many pathogens deadly hit the honey bee colonies, the most threatening of which are of exotic origin. *Varroa destructor* is one of the main culprits for the colony losses globally (GUZMÁN-NOVOA *et al.*, 2010; LE CONTE *et al.*, 2010). In many cases, this parasite has obliterated the honey bee colonies from the wild, and if we want the bees to thrive in beekeeping operations the colonies need to be properly treated with acaricides (ROSENKRANZ *et al.*, 2010).

The Italian Scientific Society BEEPATH was created in 2010 following the Master course in Bee Pathology and General Apidology held by the University of Pisa. The BEEPATH membership recalls the composition of the Master's disciples, who were mainly veterinarians, but also included agronomists, biologists, beekeepers, and researchers. The BEEPATH organs include a Scientific Commission, with the role of promoting good beekeeping practices and bee welfare, supporting health policies, implementing cultural initiatives and collaborations, and conducting research initiatives. Within BEEPATH, research is generally conducted as citizen science activities, where the available members, as non-professional investigators, conduct simplified experiments on a small number of hives under the supervision of a professional researcher. The high number of replicates distributed through-

out the country supports the territorial significance of the outcomes. Protocols, experiment journals, data, and pictures are normally shared on clouds that are made accessible to every participating member.

One of those experiments focused on Varterminator, a formic acid-based acaricide that, at the time, had been recently registered in Italy. Fifty-six colonies belonging to a total of 14 apiaries were involved in the trial. The medium efficacy resulted considerably below the threshold (90%) established in EU for the acaricides including natural substances as active ingredients (EUROPEAN MEDICINES AGENCY, 2021). Significant differences were detected in different apiaries, but no relationship was found with technical and environmental predictors. To that add negative effects consisting of unsealed brood mortality in almost 90% of the colonies and 14% queen mortality.

In a more recent experiment, the flumethrin-based acaricide PolyVar Yellow (Bayer) was tested in 14 apiaries. The application (external, at the hive entrance) was found uneasy by the majority of the participants. Despite the high efficacy reported by the literature (BLACQUIÈRE *et al.*, 20], the trial resulted in insufficient effect compared to the EU limit (95%) established for synthetic acaricides (BLACQUIÈRE *et al.*, 2017). Either type of hive or known use of pyrethroids in the area did not significantly affect the efficacy. Besides, individual environmental parameters were non-significant explanatory factors of efficacy. However, a multiple regression approach combining total rain, minimum, medium, and maximum temperature in the period of application resulted in a significant predicting model of acaricidal efficacy.

The experience within the Scientific Commission of the BEEPATH Society shows the high success of a citizen science approach to the experiments in the field of honey bee health, provided that the activity of highly motivated and well-prepared non-professional investigators is systematically surveyed by professional researchers.

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